

CULTURE AND ARTS

Nurmatov Islambek Kyzilbekovich

Teacher of the department of general education of
Jizzakh region legal technical school

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10397011>

Abstract. *This article describes in detail the relationship between culture and art, the role of culture and art in society, as well as the fact that it is one of the most important links for the development of a country to the world.*

Key words: *The festivals, culture of Uzbekistan, literature in Uzbekistan, music of Uzbekistan, dance of Uzbekistan.*

КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО

Аннотация. *В этой статье подробно описывается взаимосвязь между культурой и искусством, роль культуры и искусства в обществе, а также тот факт, что это одно из важнейших звеньев развития страны в мире.*

Ключевые слова: *фестивали, культура Узбекистана, литература Узбекистана, музыка Узбекистана, танец Узбекистана.*

INTRODUCTION

The culture of Uzbekistan is vibrant and unique—it was formed over thousands of years, incorporating the traditions and customs of the peoples who at various times inhabited the territory of modern Uzbekistan.

The ancient Persians, Greeks, Arabs, Chinese, Russians, and nomadic Turkic tribes have all contributed to Uzbek culture, which is considered the epitome of Central Asian, crossroads cultures. The traditions reflecting the multinational nature of Uzbekistan are omnipresent in its music, dance, painting, applied arts, language, cuisine, and clothing. Each region of Uzbekistan has its own unique shades as well, which are most clearly manifested in national dress and local dialects.

To get acquainted with such richness and diversity, one must travel around the whole country, but the festivals of Uzbekistan are a great events for those who want to see the whole palette of culture in this country in one place. The festivals attract creative souls from all regions of the country, and here that you can see the full assortment of Uzbek dances, music, applied arts, etc.

Art in Uzbekistan reflects the distinctive history of this country on the canvases of its masters. The wall painting at Afrosiab, for example, is one of the best examples of pre-Mongol art in the region. With the advent of Islam, however, the image of a man was banned, and the use of abstract painting grew. The art of miniatures appeared later and reached perfection over time, becoming one of the most recognizable trends in the visual arts of Uzbekistan today. Kamoliddin Behzod (16th century), Ahmad Donish (19th century), and Abdulkhalik-Mahmum (20th century) are rightly considered to be Uzbekistan's masters of miniatures. In the 20th century, there was a dramatic shift in artistic style borne out of the influence of Russian ascetics, among whom Igor Savitsky was particularly famous for creating a unique museum of painting in Nukus. In the 21st

century, the painting of Uzbekistan joined global trends, while also maintaining its unique features.

The history of literature in Uzbekistan originates from oral traditions and folklore—legends, epics and fairy tales. The tales of the bogatyr (knight-errant) Alpamysh and the inventive Nasreddin Afandi are an integral part of Uzbek culture. In the Middle Ages poets and writers whose names are now known to every inhabitant of the country appeared in Uzbekistan: Ahmad Yugnaki, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Jami, and others. The literary heritage of Uzbekistan from that era is full of poetry and most works explore the themes of love, happiness, and wisdom. In the 19th and 20th centuries, satirical and more serious, dramatic works became popular in Uzbekistan. The most famous Uzbek writers of the 20th century are Furkat, Gafur Ghulam, Mukimi, Hamid Alimzhan, Zulfiya, Abdullah Kahhar, and several dozen others. The modern literature of Uzbekistan is very diverse, but unfortunately not as popular as the classical canon.

The music of Uzbekistan, with its close ties to folklore and Uzbek poetry, is a unique manifestation of the ancient culture of the Uzbek people. Shashmak, a special genre of music in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan, which was included by UNESCO in the list of masterpieces of oral and intangible cultural heritage of mankind, is especially noteworthy. Classical and modern popular music have some similarities with generally accepted world music but maintain their own unique flavor due to the special sound of Uzbek musical instruments. The most famous musical instruments of Uzbekistan are karnay, surnay, dutar and doira. Today, Uzbek folk music can be heard at weddings, gala events, concerts, as well as at the famous Sharq Taronalari Festival, which is held every two years in Samarkand.

Uzbek dances are the personification of the beauty of the Uzbek people and culture in Uzbekistan. Uzbek folk dances differ from other regional dances in that they have a special focus on hand movements and facial expressions. Each part of Uzbekistan has its own dance schools—in some, sharp movements prevail, while others are smooth and graceful; likewise, some prefer to use a short step, while others go for something like running. Today, there are three main schools of Uzbek dance: Khorezm, Bukhara and Fergana. It is quite easy to observe Uzbek dances—not a single celebration is complete without them and everyone loves to dance! The flavor of Uzbek dance can also be appreciated at the folklore show, which is held daily during the tourist season in the building of the Nadir Divan-Begi Madrasah in Bukhara.

Uzbek crafts are one of the most popular parts of culture, giving tourists a lot of options when choosing souvenirs. Uzbek artisans pass on the secrets of craftsmanship from generation to generation, and their works are of high quality and extraordinary elegance. Blacksmiths, potters, weavers, carvers, and many others create works of art from silk, clay, wood, and metal that are recognizable throughout the world thanks to their smooth lines, geometrically perfect patterns, and harmony of form. The most famous masters of Uzbekistan are the ceramists of Gijduvan and Rishtan, the blacksmiths of Bukhara and Chust, the weavers of Margilan, and the winemakers of Samarkand. Artisans often arrange master classes in their workshops and show collections of their works in which you can get acquainted with the best creations of their fathers and grandfathers

Authentic cultural and historical monuments of Uzbekistan, along with folk art, traditions, and customs, are inscribed in the UNESCO World Heritage List. Thousands of tourists from

different countries come to look at the medieval buildings of Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva, and Shakhrisabz.

Even if you have never been to Uzbekistan, you must have heard about some of the intangible cultural heritage that was born in this country. For example, the traditional dish Palov and fabrics - satin and adras, which world-famous fashion designers such as Oscar de la Renta, Nicolas Ghesquière, and John Galliano used to create their famous collections.

The UNESCO list of the intangible cultural heritage of humanity from Uzbekistan includes 12 elements:

The cultural space of the Boysun region was recognized by UNESCO as a masterpiece of intangible cultural heritage in 2001, and in 2008 it was included in the UNESCO representative list.

Shashmaqom is a style that combines singing and playing musical instruments. It was named an intangible cultural heritage of mankind in 2003, and in 2008 entered the representative list.

Navruz is an ancient Zoroastrian holiday dedicated to the coming of spring. It has been on the UNESCO list since September 30, 2009, and in 2016 it was replenished with other countries, including Uzbekistan.

Katta Ashula is a singing genre of the inhabitants of the Ferghana Valley. It was listed in 2009.

The art of wit Askiya, was listed in 2014.

Plov: tradition and culture of cooking (was included in 2016).

The practice of the Margilan Handicraft Center for the production of atlas and adras in the traditional way (included in 2017).

Lazgi (lyazgi) - Khorazm dance (included in 2019).

The Art of Miniature (listed in 2020).

Bakhshi art - national stories with traditional music (included in 2021).

Sericulture and traditional production of silk for weaving (included in 2022).

Traditional stories and anecdotes about Hodja/ Molla Nesreddin (included in 2022).

The cultural space of the Boysun region is located in the Surkhandarya region one of the most ancient places in Central Asia, where the trade caravans of the Great

Silk Road to India passed. In the Boysun region, there are unique archeological monuments: the Teshik-Tash cave, the Payonkurgan fortress of the Kushans, the Kurganzol fortress of the era of Alexander the Great, rock paintings in the Kugitang mountains, Surkhi gorge, dinosaur footprints and much more.

Shashmaqom is a combination of poetry and music, which demonstrates the rich cultural heritage of the Uzbeks. Shashmaqom was created no later than the 11th century (according to some sources before the beginning of the 7th century). In the XVIII-XIX centuries, Shashmaqom was the main musical direction in Samarkand, Bukhara, and other large cities of modern Uzbekistan. Shashmaqom is also included in the UNESCO list of Tajikistan.

Navruz was included in the list of intangible heritage of mankind from Uzbekistan and 11 other countries. It is an ancient Zoroastrian holiday. Navruz is the celebration of the New Year, which begins on March 21. On this day, it is customary to treat loved ones with delicious food

and exchange gifts. Folk festivals with fairs and national games are held in the cities of Uzbekistan. During the Navruz holiday, it is customary to cook sumalak, a sweet festive dish made from germinated wheat germ.

Katta Ashula, which literally means “big song”, is a genre of a traditional song that is typical for the inhabitants of the Ferghana Valley. It is a combination of oriental poetry, singing, playing musical instruments, as well as sacred rites. An integral element of the performance is a small tray or porcelain plate, which directs the sound toward the audience.

Askiya, the art of wit is a unique genre of oral art, during which the participants conduct a dialogue and argue on a given topic without affecting the honor of opponents. The genre was born in the Fergana region not later than the 15th century. The participants must master the art of improvisation, demonstrate the richness of the Uzbek language, and skillfully use humor.

The culture and traditions of making Palov - with this name, a favorite dish of Uzbek people was inscribed on the list of UNESCO. Palov is a necessary part of weddings, commemorations, holidays, and folk festivals. During religious holidays, it is customary to treat Palov to the needy and the poor. The list of ingredients for Palov is simple: rice, meat, vegetables, and spices, combined in the correct sequence. But to cook a delicious dish out of them, worthy of being included in the UNESCO list, you need to have great skill and, of course, put a piece of your soul into the cooking process.

The Margilan center for the development of crafts – the local atlas and adras is highly appreciated by the world community. Atlas and adras fabrics began to be made many centuries ago in Margilan, which today is located on the territory of the Fergana region. Over the past 100 years, the practice of skillfully handcrafting fabrics has begun to be lost. That is why in 2007 a Center for the Development of Crafts was created in Margilan, the main goal of which is to preserve and revive the traditions of making atlas and adras.

Khorezm dance Lazgi (lyazgi) is an ancient form of art of the Khorezm region. In the ancient settlement of Toprak-kala, which existed in the 1st-6th centuries on the territory of modern Karakalpakstan, scientists discovered images of this dance. Lazgi is often performed while singing national songs that contain words about love and friendship.

The art of miniature is a special kind of Uzbek art, which is expressed in the creation of small paintings. Uzbekistan entered the UNESCO World Heritage List with this site along with Azerbaijan, Iran, and Turkey. Usually, the miniatures depict people, as well as national ornaments. Today miniatures can be seen on textiles, books, ceramics, papier-mache, walls, and carpets.

The art of Bakhshi is epic poetry, which is read to the accompaniment of national Uzbek musical instruments: dombra and kobuz. Stories originate from folk tales, legends, and fairy tales. The art of Bakhshi is passed down from generation to generation and is also taught in specialized schools.

Sericulture and traditional production of silk for weaving - Uzbekistan shares this element of cultural heritage with Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Iran, Turkey, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. Silk has been grown in Central Asia since the 5th-6th centuries, although some historians have earlier evidence. In Uzbekistan, a full cycle of silk production is carried out, from growing mulberry trees to dyeing silk threads and making fabrics, carpets, and curtains.

Uzbekistan shares the value of traditional stories and anecdotes about Khoja Nasreddin with Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkey, and Turkmenistan. Khoja Nasreddin is a folk hero who finds himself in funny and instructive situations. Many stories related to this character are known to both adults and children.

We recommend learning about the non-material culture of Uzbekistan during a visit to this country. Be sure to try the traditional Uzbek Palov, get acquainted with the oriental culture, and take a piece of Uzbekistan's intangible heritage with you.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that in the developing Uzbekistan, art and culture have existed since ancient times, hundreds of years ago. The art of Uzbekistan has been surprising the whole world for centuries. Over the years, the Uzbek people have brought art to its highest level. It would not be wrong to say that there are unforgettable creations in all fields of music, painting, weaving, pottery, painting. The works of Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and other masters have been historically notable outside the country and still continue to stir interest of lovers of the beautiful from all over the world. Many schools of suzané embroidery and ceramics, skullcaps of different type and purpose, national pichak-knives for every occasion, silk and woolen carpets, silk and chasing – the wonderful works, produced by local masters for centuries, make a unique exoticism of Uzbekistan.

Sui generis centers and schools of folk arts and crafts were formed in the territory of Uzbekistan for centuries. Each region has its own direction. Chust, Namangan region, is widely known for its skullcaps and knives; Rishtan, Fergana region, turquoise ceramics; ancient Margilan, satin with iridescent play of colors; sacred Bukhara, gold embroidery.

Uzbekistan has been developing arts and crafts from century to century, handing down the unique works of famous and unknown artists, which strike with the wealth of artistic imagination and perfection of shapes.

REFERENCES

1. Mavrulov A. The general state of culture of Uzbekistan in the modern process: problems, directions of development (1970-1990) // nauka publishing house. doct. scientific gorge diss. – T. 1993;
2. Mavrulov A., Dekhkonov I. Nationalism and internationalism in culture // Problems of culture and spirituality. – T., 1994. – B. 9-18. Cultural history. Textbook. – T.: "Teacher", 2007
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 1, 2018 No. PP-3990 "on holding the International Festival of melon art"
4. Performance of Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the International Festival bakhshichilik. April 6, 2019
5. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on holding an international Status Conference" dated April 6, 2018.
6. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On cultural activities and cultural organizations" dated January 20, 2020.
7. Newspaper "Culture". 2021 years

8. Rajabov T. I., Rutamova M. F. The Formation of the Spiritual and Moral Qualities of Students through Folk Songs in Continuing Education is an Urgent Pedagogical Problem //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 404-408.
9. Rajabov, T. I. (2022). THE ROLE OF BUKHARA FOLKLORE SONGS IN YOUTH EDUCATION IN THE SYSTEM OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(1), 884-889.
10. Rajabov, T. I., & Rajabov, J. I. (2022). The Formation of Spiritual and Moral Qualities of Students through Folk Songs is an Urgent Pedagogical Problem. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 2(1), 331-335.
11. Islomovna M. F. et al. DESIGNING THE METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF THE TEACHING PROCESS OF COMPUTER GRAPHICS FOR THE SPECIALTY OF ENGINEER-BUILDER //Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business & Government. – 2021. – Т. 27. – №. 4
12. Shadieva, S. S., Borieva, D. I., & Rakhimova, M. A. (2022). The Importance of Agricultural Mapping in Soil Science. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 2(3), 5-8.
13. Yunusov, R., Ganieva, F. A., Artikova, M. I., & Atayeva, Z. A. (2022). THE DEPENDENCE OF THE GROWTH, DEVELOPMENT AND PRODUCTIVITY OF APPLE TREES ON THE FACTORS OF CARE ON LOW-SALINE SOILS OF THE BUKHARA REGION. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(02), 773-781.
14. Ruziev D. Y. The Emergence of New Forms of Musical Ensembles in Uzbekistan//EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. –2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 343-346.
15. Рамазанова, У. Х., & Рахматова, М. О. (2020). SOCIAL NORMS, SANCTIONS AND PERSONALITY. Вестник науки и образования, (21-2), 115-118.
16. Ramazanova, O. K., & qizi Mustaqimova, G. G. (2022). Formation and Development of National Musical Traditions. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 2(1), 336-339.
17. Kayumov I.F. Psixologicheskie istoki muzyki // Academy. 62:11 (2020). С. 56-58.
18. Kayumov Ibroxim Fayzulloevich, Juraeva Maftuna PLACE OF MUSIC IN EDUCATION OF SPIRITUAL-SPIRITUAL COUNTRIES 5-7 KLASSOV OBshchEOBRAZOVATEL'NYX SCHOOL // Problems of pedagogy. 2020. №3 (48). URL:
19. Gaybullaevich N. F. THE ROLE OF FOLKLORE IN THE RAISING OF CHILDREN.
20. NURULLAYEV, F. (2021). Teaching Bukhara Children Folk Songs in Music Lessons as an Actual Problem. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 4(4).
21. Olimov, S. S., & Mamurova, D. I. (2021). Graphic Information Processing Technology and its Importance. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 10, 1-4.